

IN THE WORKS OF GREAT THINKERS MUSIC EDUCATION

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Annotation: *This article discusses the teaching of music education in Turkic scientists works, feelings of life the song of “Devon”, knowledge of people human development .*

Key words: *hospitality, kindness knowledge song proverbs music education methods greed ignorance.*

The view of our people an education and behavior are widely described in the works of the great scientist and thinker Mahmud Qashqari , who lived and worked in the XI century “Devonu lug`atit turk”. These works provide an Arabic translation of the words that were part of the ancient Turkic peoples. This book can be called a dictionary of the ancient Turkic language. The songs in “Devon” reflect natural landscapes and fighting, feelings of love, and advice. There are many poems in the poems that promote the value of knowledge respect for educated people ,hospitality, kindness courage, bravery, selfishness, greed, betrayal of friends and people. Such poems show that the Turkic peoples from ancient times paid great attention to education in the formation of human personality. In particular, the idea of encouraging the acquisition of knowledge, its benefits, and respect for the intellect is central to the teachings. It is advisable to approach young scientists and get advice from them.”Devonu lug`atit turk “ contains articles describing the educational experience of the people. In the proverbs, as in the songs, friendship and cooperation love of work, encouragement to acquire knowledge and profession patriotism and a sense of kinship the importance of thrift, justice and injustice consequences of good and evil rules of conduct teachings on health are interpreted. Thus the poetic passages songs proverbs in the work .”Devonu lug`atit turk “, which serve the improve people promoted goodness and had a great impact on the development of man. In this regard , Mahmud Kashgari`s work .”Devonu lug`atit turk “ still plays an important role in educating young people.

Yusuf Khas Hajib was born in Balasogun, one of the largest cities in Central Asia. Details about his life have not reached us. But he was a world –renowned thinker with his work “Knowledge that leads to happiness” written in 1069-1070.

“Qutadg`u bilig” is a textbook on education and upbringing morality, which combines the guidelines methods and measures of spiritual maturity. In this play the thinker expressed his ethical –political and scientific views.

In Yusuf Khos Khojib's *Qutadg'u bilig* the issue of human perfection is a central issue. In this play the problems of a person's place, duties and responsibilities in society and life are described in a unique way. The thinker stays after the traditional beginning of the book that the true happiness of man is in knowledge. In addition to thinking about the importance of science in a number of chapters, there are separate chapters dedicated to it.

But the scientist not only emphasizes the importance of science and education music education, but also highlights the place of knowledge and intelligence in practice. Yusuf Khos Khojib describes knowledge as great and learning as great. Because an intelligent person will be great a knowledgeable person will be great, adding knowledgeable people to the original category of people. The scientist says that all good deeds can be done because of science. At the same time the scientist predicts that "Knowledge will even lead to heaven". While Yusuf Khos Khojib emphasized the need to respect scholars and valued the intellect he considered the ignorant. He also thinks about the consequences of knowledge and ignorance. When a person ignorant muddle-headed crude he does evil deeds, on the contrary, when he is knowledgeable, wise and intelligent, he encourages people to acquire knowledge by describing that he will do good deeds.

Yusuf Khos Khojib believes that another and the most important aspect of human perfection is to develop him morally. The thinker illuminates his moral views that is social relations the moral relations between all strata of society, based on practice. The scientist pays great attention to the fact that in order to reach true perfection a person must be healthy not only mentally and morally but also physically. Yusuf Khos Khojib illuminates the guidelines methods and measures of human development with high artistic mastery, That is why this work still retains its scientific, enlightenment and educational significance. One of the most educational and moral works during the reign of the Qarakhanids is Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibatul- Haqayiq" (The Gift of Truth). The content of this work is the social political religious moral economic issues of its time in which as in the educational and moral works of that time such qualities as knowledge justice generosity kindness are glorified the idea of educating a mature person is promoted. The work consists of fourteen chapters. The first 4 chapters of the epic are traditionally prefaces and the main part begins with the fifth chapter. In these chapters the importance of knowledge the harm of ignorance the etiquette of language, the morality of the world, generosity and greed, humility and the most important features of morality are sung. Ahmad Yugnakiy has a place in the development of pedagogical thought with his views on human development. He created a unique system of formation of a perfect man in his work "Khibatul - haqayiq", which combines the mental and moral rules and requirements that are important for human perfection. In doing so he recognized that one of the most important and basic criteria for the perfection of man is that he should have

knowledge that is give him a mental upbringing.Spiritual and moral perfectionism them defines honesty truthfulness generosity, humility, sincerity, contentment, true friendship as the most important human qualities in a person and vice versa.

Denouncing nations such as ignorance greed lying arrogance ,tyranny , haste, and showing their evil consequences.From the above it is clear tahrt Ahmad Yugnaki`s work “Khibatul - haqayiq” leads the people especially the youth to spiritual maturity resolves conflicts between people in public life with friendly generosity kindness greed ignorance and enlightenment.Due to the fact that the enlightenment and educational issues in the work “Khibatul - haqayiq” are expressed with high artistic skil this work has not lost its significance for centuries.

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